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Phase equilibria investigations in the ternary Ti–Al–Nb system at elevated temperatures

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Introduction

Alloys based on γ -TiAl are of great interest for high temperature applications, such as turbine blades, due to their high specific strength at elevated temperatures [1], which makes these materials a desirable substitute for currently used materials. With the addition of refractory elements like Nb, Mo and W, the high temperature properties can be further improved due to their stabilizing effect on the disordered β -phase. The cubic crystal structure of the β -phase improves the hot workability of such alloys due to the availability of more independent slip planes. On the other hand, during cooling the ordered β_0 -phase is formed which inhibits an improvement of the ductility at room temperature [2]. An optimization of the alloy composition of higher-component TiAl-based alloys to achieve the best possible properties can be done either by extensive and costly trial-and-error experiments or by thermodynamic modelling in a computational CALPHAD (CALculation of PHase Diagram) approach provided that a reliable set of experimental data is available. However, such data are partly missing or the existing literature is inconsistent especially in the high-temperature range above 1000°C as is exemplified in Fig. 1 for the Ti–Al–Nb system at 1100°C [3-6].

Fig. 1: Experimentally determined partial isothermal section at 1100°C from Li et al. [3] superimposed with experimental results from Eckert et al. [4], Bendersky et al. [5] and Kattner et al. [6] regarding phase equilibria between the phases α_2 -Ti₃Al, γ -TiAl, β/β_0 and σ -NbAl₂

One reason for these inconsistencies could be the problem to completely quench the high-temperature phase equilibria, for example, due to the occurrence of the massive transformation of α (Ti) to γ -TiAl upon cooling. In order to tackle these problems, the European project ADVANCE was launched as a collaboration between the Max-Planck-Institut für Eisenforschung, the Helmholtz-Zentrum-Geesthacht, the Montanuniversität Leoben (Austria), and Thermo-Calc Software AB (Sweden). The project aims to optimize and improve the existing CALPHAD database for next generation Ti–Al–X alloys with sophisticated studies of phase equilibria at elevated temperatures. Alloys from eight ternary systems Ti–Al–X (X = Nb, Mo, W, Zr, Si, O, B, C) and two quaternary systems Ti–Al–Nb–Y (Y = Mo, W) will be heat-treated and investigated in detail. The first experimental results of the studies in the ternary Ti–Al–Nb system are presented here.

Materials, Methods and First Results

A series of ternary Ti–Al–Nb alloys were produced out of high-purity elements Ti (99,995 %), Al (99,999 %) and Nb (99,9%) using vacuum arc melting in high-purity Ar-atmosphere. Subsequently, the alloys were encapsulated in quartz capsules for heat treatments up to 1100°C. For higher temperatures, a special double crucible technique described by Kainuma et al. [7] was applied. Since the exact alloy composition and the impurity levels especially of oxygen and nitrogen play an important role in the determination of phase equilibria, they were cross-checked before and after the heat treatment using several methods (inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES), melt combustion and wet chemical analysis). The microstructure was examined using light optical microscopy (LOM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Utilizing powder X-ray diffraction (P-XRD), electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD), and electron probe microanalysis (EPMA), the types and compositions of all phases were determined. Phase transition temperatures were measured by differential thermal analysis (DTA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). For certain samples, these results were cross-checked using in situ synchrotron high-energy XRD (HEXRD).

Fig. 2: SEM-BSE picture of a lamellar two phase microstructure consisting of α_2 -Ti₃Al (white) + γ -TiAl (grey) after DTA measurement up to 1450°C

In Fig. 2, a lamellar microstructure from an alloy with the nominal composition Ti-45Al-5Nb (in at.%) after DTA measurement (heating- and cooling rate: 20 K/min) up to 1450°C is shown. Inside the grey γ -TiAl matrix, there are brighter α_2 -Ti₃Al lamella that form upon cooling resulting in the expected two-phase microstructure. In addition, the relatively slow cooling rate creates coarser lamella compared to water-quenched samples [2]. Further work includes heat treatments and evaluation of measured data to construct isothermal sections at different temperatures to resolve the inconsistencies in literature.

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